

A Predictive Factor Analysis of Daily Living Skills Development of Pupils with Intellectual Disability

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ABSTRACT: People with intellectual disability may experience limitations in residential and vocational placement options due to their lack of independence with daily living skills. To teach daily living skills that take advantage of people with intellectual disabilities' strengths in learning and skill retention, educators and families face a challenge. This research investigates the predictive influence of parental involvement, social support, and gender on developing daily living skills among pupils with intellectual disability. Data was collected from 150 (male = 38%; female = 62%; Mean age = 12.5; SD = 3.02) pupils with intellectual disability enrolled in special education programs in Ibadan, Nigeria. The measures used were a subjective response to parental involvement, social support and daily living skills provided by study respondents. Data analysis revealed that parental involvement and gender did not significantly relate to developing daily living skills among pupils with intellectual disability. The relationship between social support and the development of daily living skills among pupils with intellectual disability was significant (-0.290 , $p\text{-value } 0.000 < 0.05$). The joint contribution of parental involvement, social support, and gender in developing daily living skills is statistically significant ($F(3,146) = 6.157$; $p < 0.05$). Based on our research findings, it is imperative to note that social support is critical in facilitating the development of daily living skills for students with intellectual disabilities.

Key words: Parental involvement, social support, gender, daily living skills, pupils with intellectual disability

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1. Introduction

Pupils with intellectual disability (ID) are at increased risk of co-occurring diagnoses, which limits their ability to live an everyday life. Parents, educators, and healthcare professionals recognize the importance of daily living skills for this group of learners. Developing daily living skills among people with ID may be lost or not generalised across environments

without prompting from professionals and family members (Hume et al., 2009). Children with ID may have fewer residential and vocational placement options due to their lack of daily living independence. Proper hand washing by students can reduce medical costs and lost school days due to illness and infection and can increase the loss of productivity for parents who miss work and other activities when their children miss school (Harkavy, 2009). The challenge for educators and families of children with ID is to teach daily living skills that capitalise on the learning and skill-retention strengths of people with ID.

Daily living skills (dressing and undressing, looking after oneself, toilet use, taking food independently, bathing, washing, etc.) influence a child's self-evaluation. Developing these skills is essential to socialisation, regardless of an individual's intellectual capacity (Morzhina, 2006). As a significant life competence of special education, developing pupils' adequate and self-sufficient activity is one of the main tasks of the modern stage. The dynamic of the development of individuals with ID opportunities and their adaptive abilities in the socialisation process depends on the stated problem as one of the most significant problems. A lack of daily living skills results in a person being unable to function independently, requiring the assistance of caregivers. It is possible to determine whether a child will be ready for daycare or school depending on their level of independence or the support they need to perform daily living skills (Jasmin et al., 2009). Developing daily living skills enables a child to become independent.

Thus, children are better able to make decisions independently due to these skills. In addition, they help develop a child's personality (Onder, 2003). It is important to note that adaptive behaviour encompasses the characteristics necessary for living independently, including communication, interpersonal, and daily living skills (e.g., dressing and grooming oneself). Adaptive skills develop over time, so older children tend to have higher levels (Loveland & Tunali-Kotoski, 1998). Individuals with mild ID can benefit from functional academic skills and social/vocational training when instructional strategies consider their learning characteristics. (Jacob et al., 2022). Several studies have demonstrated that cognitive level and adaptive behaviour are positively correlated, with stronger correlations occurring in cases with more severe ID (De Bildt et al., 2005; Vig & Jedrysek, 1995). It is crucial to examine the daily functioning of individuals with ID more closely as they mature, including their adaptive behaviour.

Personal independence, social responsibility, and the ability to interact with others in different environments are necessary for developing adaptive behaviours. A high priority should be placed on socialisation, communication, and daily living skills (DLS) (Burger-Caplan et al., 2018; Sparrow & Cicchetti, 1985). Fundamental movement skills play a significant role in the daily living skills of children and adolescents with ID. Deficits or delays in fundamental movement skills can impact the daily living abilities of individuals with ID. An individual's ability to operate in social settings is reflected in socialisation. Interactions with others involve exchanging information (Sparrow & Cicchetti, 1985). Effective interventions are needed for students with ID (Shapiro, 2011; Jacob & Pillay, 2022). This study focuses on the effect of parental involvement, social support, and gender as predictors of daily living skills (DLS).

2. Literature review

Parental involvement and daily living skills development

Parents' involvement in their children's education is behaviour supporting social/emotional development at home and school (El Nokali et al., 2010; Goleman, 1998). Parents face a wide range of complex challenges today. Often, parents find it difficult to balance the demands of their time with the needs of their children because of the fast-paced nature of their children's day-to-day lives. Parents can help their children develop DLS by acquiring fluency in parent-implemented interventions (PII), which are practices in which professionals teach their parents intervention procedures for delivering part or all of a given intervention to their children (Wong et al., 2013).

Parental involvement can be seen in various ways, for example, in completing homework or children's homework (Benner et al., 2016; McNeal Jr., 2015; Silinskas & Kikas, 2019), providing stimulation and learning enrichment activities (Benner et al., 2016), and involvement in parent-teacher organizations (Benner et al., 2016; McNeal Jr., 2015). Parental involvement can also be referred to as parental participation, educational partnership, and engagement (Hakyemez-Paul et al., 2018). Partnerships between parents and teachers and partnerships between parents and practitioners are used interchangeably (Hujala et al., 2009; Alasuutari, 2010). Epstein (2010) provides a model for teacher-parent relationships that describes the teacher-parent relationship as one based on communication and cooperation and parental involvement as malleable based on the practices of teachers, administrators, other parents, and students in ongoing research on parental involvement.

Fan and Chen (2001) state that parental involvement is associated with positive educational outcomes for general students. Jeynes's (2005) meta-analysis shows that parental involvement in urban student populations is strongly related to academic outcomes. Behavioral and cognitive engagement of urban middle-school students is positively associated with parental involvement (Dotterer & Wehrspann, 2016). Therefore, parental involvement contributed to cognitive development and behavior associated with daily living, indicating the importance of parental involvement in developing appropriate daily living skills. The involvement of parents in their children's education has been linked with higher academic outcomes for youth, so parental educational involvement can be a promising avenue for improving young people's educational prospects (Jeynes, 2007; Hill & Tyson, 2009). Parents' involvement in youth education varies by type (Fan & Chen, 2001; Hill & Tyson, 2009) and SES (Hill et al., 2004).

Social support and daily living skills development

It is possible to provide social support in a variety of ways. It may simply be a time to spend with one another or a form of assistance only incidentally related to the situation (Baria & Gomez, 2022). Managing stressful learning and development events or challenges is one of the benefits that it provides. In addition, early learners' progress has consistently been demonstrated to positively impact a youngster's long-term outcomes and improve career plans, educational achievement, and quality of life (Reyes et al., 2020). The anecdotal evidence indicates that students with less social support had poorer learning abilities and developmental skills. Cultural context, life events, individual characteristics,

and the relationship between the provider and recipient determine the appropriateness of perceived social support (Jacob et al., 2021).

This support system is crucial in nurturing the students' overall growth, allowing them to thrive academically and in their personal and social development. The involvement and encouragement from family members, educators, and classmates contribute to the students' ability to develop essential life skills, such as communication, teamwork, and resilience, which are invaluable for their future success. Family members not providing enough support to students often leads to problems at school, such as bullying and poor health (Blažević, 2016). It is believed that belief in social experiences has aided in fulfilling emotional or instrumental needs, including motivation to adopt healthily and reduce risky behaviors, feelings of being understood, assessment of potentially stressful events as less threatening, enhanced sense of control or mastery; increased self-esteem; use of active coping strategies; and the impact of social influence and social comparison (Southwick et al., 2016).

Social support has a compelling impact on individualism and collectivist civilizations (Akcinar & Baydar, 2016). Social support is a significant proximal context component that influences student learning and results from expectancies. A perceived social support environment can be defined as an atmosphere that offers appropriate support if needed or helps teach a particular school domain (Baria & Gomez, 2022). Human happiness is correlated with social life, as evidenced by an increasing body of research (Rice et al., 2013). Cultural context, life events, individual characteristics, and the relationship between the provider and recipient determine the appropriateness of perceived social support (Chronister et al., 2006; Jacob et al., 2021). Support needs related to daily living are paramount for individuals with ID. Work supporters may sometimes struggle to provide sufficient support in this area, emphasizing the importance of effectively understanding and addressing these needs (Maebara et al., 2022). Additionally, interventions focusing on daily living skills have been shown to positively impact individuals with ID over the long term (Burns et al., 2019).

Gender and daily living skills development

Students' performance is also thought to be affected significantly by their gender. The performance of boys and girls differs in many studies (O'Reilly & McNamara, 2007; Abubakar & Bada, 2012). The gender role in performance remains a topic of increased scientific interest, mainly because the reported findings are inconclusive, despite the compelling evidence regarding the effect of other individual and contextual factors on performance. Study findings indicate that student's achievement is not significantly different based on gender. Else-Quest et al. (2010) concluded that standardised mathematics tests show negligible gender differences. According to Ajai and Imoko (2015), achievement and retention scores in mathematics did not differ significantly between male and female students.

In addition to examining school grades and performance, other aspects of academic life have been investigated for the gender gap in academic performance. Among other things, Bugler et al. (2015) found that women were more motivated and adapted to their

environment than men. The study conducted by Ghazvini and Khajehpour (2011) also found that female students had a more significant internal locus of control over academic performance than male students. Based on the research findings, there were no discernible differences in academic self-concept between genders. Moreover, girls take greater responsibility for their academic failures than boys and use learning strategies less frequently than boys.

According to Martin (2007), over 12,000 students responded to the Student Motivation and Engagement Scale in a study; several positive aspects of motivation are higher for girls than for boys, including the value of school, emphasis on learning, planning, task management, and persistence. A study also found that girls were more anxious than boys (Martin & Marsh, 2005). Disengagement (another maladaptive aspect of academic motivation) and self-handicapping (self-sabotage) favoured boys over girls. Academic motivation is expected to be higher among girls. According to Skinner et al. (2008), girls reported significantly higher levels of emotional and behavioural engagement, while boys reported significantly higher levels of dissatisfaction. There has been evidence of gender differences in motivation in various academic subjects, including English, mathematics, foreign languages, and sports (Eccles et al., 1993; Jacobs et al., 2002; Williams et al., 2002). In general, girls are more motivated than boys, except in sports.

Research Questions

- What is the relationship between independent variables (parental involvement, social support, and gender) and the dependent variable (daily living skills) of pupils with moderate ID?
- What is the relative contribution of independent variables (parental involvement, social support, and gender) and dependent variable (daily living skills) of pupils with moderate ID?
- What is the joint effect of independent variables (parental involvement, social support and gender) and dependent variable (daily living skills) of pupils with moderate ID?

3. Methodology

Design and respondents

The study adopted descriptive research using a correlational design. One hundred and fifty pupils with ID (aged range 8 - 18 years, 57 (38%) =male and 93 (62%) = female) were selected as study respondents from special schools in Ibadan, Nigeria. For this study, total enumeration was used because there were relatively few learners with ID attending special schools. Respondents for the study were all students identified as having ID and their parents in the schools visited.

Method of data collection

Study respondents were identified as pupils with moderate ID by a psychologist who assessed their intelligence quotient for placement using Slosson Intelligence. Parents/caregivers and school administrators were contacted for respondents' participation in the study. The study's intent was appropriately explained to parents and caregivers, while

explicit instructions were provided on what respondents should do. A confidentiality agreement was provided to parents and caregivers. The respondents were organized with the assistance of two research assistants. An average of an hour was needed to complete the questionnaire.

Measures

The study collected data on the independent variables (parental involvement, social support, and gender) and the dependent variable (daily living skills). The respondents' demographic characteristics collected include age and gender. The scale was tagged "Peer influence, social acceptance, gender and aggressive behavior of learners with ID."

The parental Involvement Scale (Bradley-Geist & Olson-Buchanan, 2014) measures parental involvement in their child's education and social life. It was developed to study the correlates of over-parenting among undergraduate students. Participants were asked to answer nine questions regarding their parents' involvement. The items were designed to assess the frequency with which one's parents or guardians initiate involvement with one's school and social life. This ranged from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The analysis showed that the scale was unidimensional and that the reliability (0.86) was acceptable.

Social Support Scale: Social support is widely recognized as a psychological resource that can help one cope with stress (Krause & Borawski-Clark, 1995). Received Support scales include Tangible Support, such as help with transportation (3 items); Emotional Support, such as having others listen and show interest (4 items); and Informational Support, such as sharing suggestions and information (4 items). Satisfaction with Support (3 items) and Negative Social Interaction, such as criticisms and demands by others (3 items), are also included. Although the scales are brief, their psychometrics are good, with alpha coefficients over .7 for all subscales. In several studies, these scales have been found to have construct validity. Positive caregiving outcomes have been attributed to improved social support satisfaction (Roth et al., 2005; Cho et al., 2015).

Daily living skills rating scale: Researcher's version

The researcher developed the daily living skills rating scale to measure study participants' acquisition level of daily living skills. The scale consists of 20 core tasks categorized into four domains. The researcher ensured the content and face validity of the scale. The reliability coefficient of the rating scale ranges from 0.91, indicating that scale validity and utility are well established.

Procedure for Data Collection

A psychologist used Slosson Intelligence to assess the intelligence quotients of pupils identified as respondents to the present study. Participation of the identified respondents was subject to informed consent by parents/caregivers and school administrators. In addition to providing parents and caregivers with information about the study's purpose, explicit instructions were provided to guide respondents regarding what they should do. Parents were assured that the study information would remain confidential.

The respondents were organised with the assistance of two research assistants. On average, it took about an hour to complete the questionnaire.

Ethical Consideration

The relevant education district in Ibadan approved data collection for the study. The parents and/or caregivers of the pupils selected for the study were contacted through the management of the special school and rehabilitation centre the pupils attend. This study was conducted with the permission of the parents of these pupils. Moreover, no individual respondent was exposed to physical or psychological risks. The study's purpose was explained to the respondents, parents, and caregivers. The respondents' mental ability was considered due to their ID. They were briefed about the process and their participation. Due to the participants' ages, parents were required to complete an informed consent form to enable their children to participate as respondents. This study adhered strictly to the ethical standards of research.

Method of analysis

An analysis of the data generated was conducted using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics of the correlation matrix at a significance level of 0.05. For inferential analysis, we used Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression. The first research question was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, while the second and third questions were analyzed using multiple regression analysis.

RQ1: What is the relationship between independent variables (parental involvement, social support, and gender) and dependent variable (daily living skills) of pupils with moderate ID?

Table 1: Correlation between parental involvement, social support and gender on daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID

Variable	1	2	3	4
Daily living skills	1			
Parental involvement (P value)	.020 .812	1		
Social support (p-value)	-.290** .000	-.150 .067	1	
Gender (p-value)	-.059 .477	.225** .006	-.352** .000	1
Mean	38.71	57.42	28.76	1.48
Standard Deviation	4.86	3.46	7.12	0.50

The results in Table 1 show the Pearson correlation analysis. Social support value yielded -0.290, with a negative relationship to daily living skills and significance with the p -value $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows a positive significant relationship. This implies that social support is negatively related to the daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID. Furthermore, the parental involvement value is 0.020, which shows a positive relationship with the daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID and is not significant, with the p -value $0.812 > 0.05$. The results from the table also indicated that gender is negatively and not correlated with the

daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID ($r = -0.059$, $p\text{-value } 0.477 > 0.05$). Implies that pupils with moderate ID exhibited daily living skills when society supported them.

RQ2: What is the relative contribution of independent variables (parental involvement, social support, and gender) and dependent variable (daily living skills) of pupils with moderate ID?

Table 2: Relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variables
(Test of significance of the regression coefficients)

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	47.563	6.807		6.987	.000
Parental involvement	.012	.113	.009	.107	.915
Social support	-.240	.057	-.352	-4.210	.000
Gender	-1.781	.824	-.183	-2.161	.032

Table 2 reveals the significant relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable, expressed as beta weights. The relative of social support on daily living skills. The standardized regression coefficient was used to determine the relative contributions of the independent variables. Social support ($\beta = -.352$, $t = -4.210$, $p < 0.05$) is the prediction's most potent contributor. It has a negative relative contribution to the daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID. In contrast, parental involvement ($\beta = 0.009$, $t = 0.107$, $p > 0.05$) has no relative contribution to daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID, and gender ($\beta = -0.183$, $t = -2.161$, $p < 0.05$) has a negative and significant relative contribution to daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID. It implies that there was a negative relative contribution of social support and gender on the daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID.

RQ3: What is the joint effect of independent variables (parental involvement, social support and gender) and dependent variable (daily living skills) of pupils with moderate ID?

Table 3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Composite Effect of the Independent Variable on the Dependent Variable

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Regression	396.190	3	132.063	6.157	.001	Significant
Residual	3110.400	146	21.451			
Total	3506.591	149				

R = .336
 $R^2 = .113$
Adjusted $R^2 = .095$

Table 3 shows that the independent and dependent variables have a composite relationship ($R = 0.33$). It also revealed that although the independent variables significantly impact the dependent variable, they only account for a small portion of the variance. Consequently, the independent variables accounted for 11.3% of the total variance in daily living skills (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.113$). The model's moderate R and R-squared values indicate that other factors that influence the dependent variable are likely not considered in the model. It may

be necessary to conduct further analysis to enhance the model's explanatory ability. Furthermore, the combined effect is statistically significant ($F(3,146) = 6.157; p < 0.05$). Therefore, the composite influence of the independent variables, parental involvement, social support and gender accounted for 11.3% of the variation in the daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID.

4. Discussion of findings

This study shows no correlation between parental involvement and daily life skills, inconsistent with many studies examining the effects of parental involvement on wards' performance at the global and type-specific levels (Fan & Chen, 2001; Jeynes, 2007; Hill & Tyson, 2009). The significant positive correlation between parental involvement and daily living skills underscores the importance of engaging parents or guardians in the development and support processes of pupils with moderate ID. There is also evidence in the literature that mothers' practices that support children's daily living skills are associated with their school attendance. There is a greater tendency for children who spend less time in kindergarten to have a more supportive mother at home in terms of their daily living skills. In comparison to their peers, children whose mothers provided them with more support in daily living skills showed significant improvements in daily living skills (Kaçan et al., 2019).

Moreover, interventions focusing on daily living skills have demonstrated positive long-term effects on individuals with ID (Burns et al., 2019). The negative correlation between social support and daily living skills is intriguing. It might suggest that the type or quality of social support matters more than its quantity or that it interacts with other factors (like gender) in complex ways that might mitigate its benefits. The reason may also be that workplace coworkers face challenges in providing adequate support in this area. Maebara et al. (2022) highlight the significance of accurately comprehending and addressing these needs.

Gender's non-significant correlation with daily living skills but significant correlations with the other variables indicates that gender-specific experiences or societal roles might influence how parental involvement and social support impact these pupils. The results reveal multifaceted relationships between parental involvement, social support, gender, and daily living skills in pupils with moderate ID, suggesting areas for further research and potential interventions to improve outcomes.

Researchers found that preschool children who ate with family members used forks, spoons, and daily living skills more efficiently and used them more (Oğuz & Derin, 2013). A study found that mothers who spend more time with their children contribute significantly to their development of daily living skills (Demiriz & Dinçer, 2001). The study found a statistically significant difference between the children's daily living skills based on parental involvement.

The results show insignificant relationships between the respondents' social support and daily living. This aligns with the previous submission on the effectiveness of social support in various areas of individuals' lives. According to research that uses the primary effect model, individuals with regular social interactions with diverse relationship partners

have a positive effect, a sense of stability, and self-worth, all positive predictors of psychological well-being in general (Thoits, 1983). There is also evidence that social support can lessen the psychological effects of stressful events (the stress-buffering effect model; Cohen & Wills, 1985).

Life satisfaction and well-being are consistently higher for individuals with close and supportive spouses, friends, and families (Chen & Feeley, 2014), as well as fewer stress-related and health-related costs, such as social isolation and depression (Okabayashi et al., 2004; Sherman et al., 2011). Conversely, insufficient social support contributes to emotional distress, depression, and mortality (Yang et al., 2014). Students' interactions with teachers and peers at school likely influence the relationship between adolescents' social goals and behaviour. Relationships between students and teachers have been associated with social adjustment outcomes, including aggression, misconduct, and prosocial behaviour (Wentzel et al., 2016). There is no significant relationship between gender and the daily living skills of study respondents. The result revealed that gender as a variable did not contribute to developing daily living skills.

However, when considered with other variables, it jointly contributed to daily living skills. Conflicting findings regarding gender differences in achievement have hampered our understanding of the issue. Many subject matter tests conducted during the early school years do not show any effect of gender on achievement disparity. Gender plays a significant role in achievement disparities in middle school, which becomes fully apparent in high school and beyond (Entwisle et al., 1997; Hyde et al., 1990; Willingham & Cole, 1997). Conversely, others have found consistent gender differences at the elementary level, particularly in literacy scores (Coley, 2001; Ready et al., 2005). A significant gender gap favours girls in classroom grades in English, math, and social studies, but a non-existent or small gap favours boys on standardised achievement and intelligence tests (Duckworth & Seligman, 2006). Considering this conflicting evidence, we should examine possible factors that may help eliminate confusion from the research literature and force us to examine the actual state of gender differences in achievement.

5. Conclusion

This research has established that parental involvement, social support and gender jointly contributed to the daily living skills of pupils with ID. The daily living skills of the study participants were not significantly influenced by parental involvement or gender. However, social support contributed significantly to the development of daily living skills. Based on the study's findings, additional research is needed to identify factors influencing respondents' daily living skills. This study was not interested in the predictive influence of psychological and environmental factors on the daily living skills of the participants. Due to the unique characteristics of pupils with ID, the study was limited to a small sample size.

The study's descriptive research design and the limited number of respondents constrain the generalizability of the findings. The study examined the relationship between parental involvement, social support, gender, and daily living skills of pupils with moderate ID in Ibadan, Nigeria, which is just one state out of 36 states in the country. The findings may be restricted to pupils with moderate ID in Ibadan, Nigeria, due to cultural differences

in the various states of the federation. The relationship between dependent variables (parental involvement, social support, and gender) and the daily living skills of pupils with moderate intellectual disabilities has not been studied before. Therefore, the researchers do not have any other studies to compare their findings with. As a result, it is crucial to interpret the results with caution.

6. Limitations

One significant constraint of the study is its reliance on a sample size drawn solely from special education programs in Ibadan, Nigeria. This limited geographical scope and modest sample size raise concerns about the generalizability of the findings to the broader population of individuals with ID. Furthermore, the study relies heavily on subjective measures to determine the significant relationship the independent variables (parental involvement, social support and gender) have with daily living skills among respondents. Although these subjective responses yield valuable perspectives, they are intrinsically vulnerable to biases and varied interpretations, potentially skewing the outcome.

Another notable limitation arises from the study's cross-sectional design, which, by capturing data at a single point in time, restricts the ability to deduce causal relationships or observe the evolution of daily living skills over an extended period. Such designs lack a longitudinal narrative of how these factors interplay and shape skill development as the pupil ages. Moreover, the focus of the research on parental involvement, social support, and gender as the sole predictive factors overlooks an array of other consequential factors.

Elements such as families' economic standing, the severity of the disability, accessibility to resources, and individualized education plans (IEPs) tailored to pupils' requirements could also significantly mold the development of daily living skills, yet remain unexplored in this analysis. Additionally, the potential sway of confounding variables, which could noticeably impact the outcomes, is not sufficiently controlled for or acknowledged within the study's framework. Factors like the quality of the educational program, educator expertise, and pupil-teacher ratios, though pivotal, are not accounted for, possibly detracting from the preciseness of the findings.

The study's operational definitions and measurement of key variables like parental involvement and social support also pose a challenge. Relying on self-reported measures may not fully encapsulate the multifaceted nature of these constructs, calling into question the clarity and reliability of the research conclusions. Addressing these limitations in future research endeavors—by broadening the sample to encompass a more varied population, integrating mixed methods to incorporate both subjective and objective data, considering a fuller spectrum of predictive factors, and adopting longitudinal designs—could significantly enhance understanding and provide a richer, more accurate depiction of the factors influencing the development of daily living skills among pupils with ID.

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